

Engineering Organic chromophores for Luminescent Solar Concentrators

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Social and economic development of modern societies strongly depends on the access to a cheap, abundant and relentless supply of energy. Compared to fossil fuels, solar energy satisfies the key requirements for an environmentally-friendly and renewable energy technology, able of reducing the dumping of CO₂ in the atmosphere. It has been estimated that ~ 40 % of the total energy consumption occurs in buildings, 70 % of which in the form of electricity. One method to tackle this issue is by making buildings. In principle buildings can be made self-sufficient in terms of energy needs by integrating solar cells into building

infrastructures such as walls and windows (building integrated photovoltaics (BIPVs)).¹ In this context, luminescent solar concentrators (LSC) have emerged as promising candidates for building integrated photovoltaics.²

Here we report synthesis and characterization organic chromophores for differently coloured luminescent solar concentrators. The fundamental studies on how their opto-electronic properties affects the performance of LSCs are presented here.

Solar cells, Luminescent solar concentrator, building integrated photovoltaics, organic chromophores

References

1. M. Debijs, Nature 519 (2015) 298-299
2. Ana Luisa Martínez et al, J. Photon. Energy 6(2016), 045504.